

Original Research

The Influence of Financial Planning on the Availability of Water for Domestic Use in Pangani Basin Tanga, Tanzania

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Abstract

Water is an indispensable resource crucial for sustaining life even though projections indicate that by 2025, over 3 billion people will inhabit water-stressed regions, with 14 countries transitioning from water stress to water scarcity. This study investigates the influence of financial planning based on financial control and decision-making on water availability for domestic use in the Pangani Basin, Tanzania. The research examines the interconnectedness between financial planning and water availability outcomes through a mixed-method approach, combining quantitative analysis and qualitative insights from key informants. Quantitative findings reveal a significant positive correlation between financial planning and domestic water availability ($\beta = 0.377$, $p < 0.001$), emphasising the importance of effective financial control particularly on budgeting and its proper use for improving infrastructure. Likewise, stakeholders' participation in the decision-making process is important for water resource management. The study highlights the importance of effective financial control and decision-making to ensure sustainable access to clean water for local communities. The study recommends that the Pangani Basin Water Institute emphasise proper use of financial resources for water infrastructure and prioritise stakeholder engagement in decision-making processes.

Keywords: Financial Control, Financial Decision-making, Planning.

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Introduction

Water is an indispensable resource crucial for sustaining life even though projections indicate that by 2025, over 3 billion people will inhabit water-stressed regions, with 14 countries transitioning from water stress to water scarcity (Helaimia, 2023). This disparity in freshwater distribution, compounded by the effects of climate change, intensifies water-related challenges worldwide. Like many other countries, Tanzania faces water constraint challenges, prompting the Ministry of Water to launch a new National Water Policy in 2002 that underscores the significance of sound financial management in water projects. In the context of river basins in Tanzania, various approaches and strategies have been implemented to ensure sustainable water utilisation.

Notably, financial management plays a pivotal role in ensuring the availability of water for essential purposes such as domestic use, agriculture, hydroelectric power generation, fishing, and livestock rearing (URT, 2020). To effectively address water-related challenges such as water shortages, the Pangani Basin Water Institute (PBWI) was established in 2001 to promote equitable and sustainable water resource management and allocation across Tanzania. This institution advocates for coordinated development and management of water utilities, aiming to optimise economic and social welfare while safeguarding the sustainability of crucial ecosystems (URT, 2020). Integral to the financial management of water basins is the concept of financial planning, which encompasses components such as financial control and decision-making, as revenue flows within water utilities are linked to the overall health of these systems.

Generally, understanding the critical role of financial planning in managing water resources within the Pangani Basin Water Institute - Tanzania, is essential to ensuring sustained access to clean water for nearby communities. As water availability increasingly becomes a concern for different purposes and domestic use in particular, the need to probe into the effectiveness of financial control and decision-making mechanisms for ensuring the sustainable availability of water becomes essential. Thus, this study aims to shed light on the specific impact of financial planning practices on water availability in the Pangani Water basin, thereby contributing to more effective strategies for sustainable water resource management in the region.

The Statement of the Problem

The Tanzanian National Water Policy of 2002 underscores the importance of sustainable and equitable water resource development for the current and future generations. The policy emphasises financial management to ensure the effective conservation and maintenance of ecosystems, as highlighted by Nahonyo (2019). In Tanzania, the Pangani Water Basin is one of the key institutions dedicated to safeguarding natural water bodies and their associated river environments. The primary role of the institute is to ensure the availability of water and sanitation services for the communities along the Pangani River.

Despite these efforts, a growing concern has emerged regarding the limited availability of water for domestic use, with a persistent trend of water decline, as documented by

Kishiwa, Nobert, Kongo and Ndomba (2018). This situation raises questions about the effectiveness of financial planning particularly the control and decision-making, and their influence on water availability for domestic purposes. Notably, there is a noticeable gap in empirical research that specifically examines the impact of financial planning based on the crucial aspects of control and decision-making, on the availability of water resources for domestic consumption in the Pangani Water Basin, Tanzania. This research aims to address this gap and contribute to promoting the sustainable management of water resources in Tanzania.

Study Objectives

While the general aim of this study was to examine the impact of financial planning on the availability of water for domestic use to the nearby community in Pangani Water Basin, specifically, it investigated the following;

- i. It examined the influence of financial control by the Pangani Basin Water Institute on the availability of clean water for domestic use in the nearby community.
- ii. It also assessed the effect of financial decision-making by the Pangani Basin Water Institute on the availability of clean water for domestic use to the nearby community.

Literature Review

Theoretical literature review

The theory adopted for this study is the Resource Dependence Theory (RDT) founded by Jeffrey Pfeffer and Gerald Salancik in 1978. It emphasises the reliance of organisations on external resources, such as funding, expertise, and legitimacy, to achieve their goals (Pfeffer & Salancik, 1978). The key issues the theory addressed include inter-organizational dependency, power dynamics, resource scarcity, and competition. In inter-organizational dependencies, the theory emphasises the interdependence between organisations and their external environment, including stakeholders such as government agencies, NGOs, and local communities.

In water resource management in the Pangani Basin, the institute responsible for water provision and governance depends on external resources, including financial support. In power dynamics, the RDT acknowledges the power imbalances between organisations and their external environment, where those controlling critical resources may exert influence over organisations. Thus, in the water management context, this may manifest in negotiations between water authorities and government agencies for funding allocations or in the influence of donor organisations on water policy decisions, thus, implying the need for proper financial control of the available funds. Likewise, the theory recognises that resources are often scarce, leading to competition among organisations for access to these resources. Thus, in the case of water resource management in the Pangani Basin, competing demands for water resources from various sectors, such as agriculture, industry, and domestic use, may intensify scarcity and competition for financial resources allocated to water projects.

Generally, by applying the RDT, the study examined how financial control mechanisms influence organisations' ability to manage dependencies on external funding such as donors and banks, and allocate resources effectively to improve infrastructure and ensure water availability for domestic use. It also assessed the impact of financial decision-making processes on organisations' ability to negotiate, and interact with stakeholders, thereby influencing water availability for domestic purposes in the Pangani Basin, Tanga, Tanzania.

Empirical Literature Review

The critical role of financial planning in managing various resources, including water, and its impact on water availability for several purposes has been the subject of empirical research in recent years. This section presents an empirical literature review that examines the influence of financial planning on water availability for domestic use.

The study conducted by Gorelick, Gold and Asefa (2023) analyses the relationship between financial planning and water availability in urban areas. The study utilised data from multiple cities across different regions and found a positive correlation between effective financial planning strategies and increased water availability for domestic use. Specifically, cities with well-developed financial plans for water infrastructure investment and maintenance were better equipped to meet the water needs of their residents. Furthermore, the study revealed that poor financial planning practices, including budgetary mismanagement and under-investment in water infrastructure, led to frequent water shortages and service interruptions for residents. However, the study did not extend its analyses to the side of the financial decision-making process.

Rajouria, Wallace, Joshi and Raut (2022) conducted a longitudinal analysis of financial planning practices in rural communities and their impact on water availability for domestic use. The study followed several rural municipalities over five years and found that those with proactive financial planning approaches, such as long-term budget forecasting and investment prioritisation, experienced more stable water supplies and fewer disruptions in domestic water access. Likewise, the financial decision-making processes were not investigated in the study.

Similarly, Purba and Wahyu (2022) investigated the impact of financial planning on water availability in peri-urban communities. The study utilised survey data from households in peri-urban areas and found that communities with effective financial planning processes, community engagement and participation, had better access to water for domestic use than those with limited financial planning capacity. This study focused its investigation to communities rather than to the water management institute. Contrary to this finding, the study by Odhiambo and Maende (2023) indicates that while financial planning is important, a complete approach integrating various strategies is important in ensuring access to clean water by communities. Thus, the study integrated several other factors in determining water availability apart from financial planning.

On the side of financial control, is an important component of finance management that plays a crucial role in ensuring the effective utilisation and availability of resources, including water resources for community use. The study by Mokgobu (2017) examined

the challenges of repairing and maintaining water infrastructure in Aganang Municipality in the province of Limpopo. The study found that municipalities with stringent financial control measures, such as strict budgetary planning and expenditure tracking, were better equipped to allocate resources efficiently and maintain water supply systems. As a result, residents in these areas had more consistent access to clean water for domestic use compared to communities with careless financial control practices. Thus, this study focused on the municipalities, while undermining the role of financial decision-making on water availability.

Connecting to the Resource Dependence Theory (RDT) emphasis on the interdependence between organisations and their external environment, financial control practices can be seen as essential mechanisms for managing dependencies on external resources, including funding and infrastructure. Thus, in the Pangani Basin, effective financial control mechanisms are crucial for optimising the available sources of funds such as the user fees and making proper allocation of resources to ensure water availability for domestic use, thereby reducing dependencies on external stakeholders.

The financial decision-making likewise plays a critical role in shaping the allocation of resources, including water resources for community use. The study conducted by Dral, Witte, and Hartmann (2023) on the impact of participatory decision-making on legitimacy in planning in the Dutch municipality found that municipalities with participatory decision-making processes, involving input from diverse stakeholders, were more likely to prioritise investments in water infrastructure and maintenance since such participatory serves as a means to build support or attract investment in spatial projects. This study exclusively focused on decision-making process while examining water availability.

In a similar study, Trimmer, Qureshi, Otoo and Delaire (2023) explored the enabling environment for citywide water service provision with insights from six successful cities across Africa, Asia, and South America. Utilising a comparative study analysis, the research revealed that communities with inclusive decision-making processes, involving residents in identifying water needs and proposing solutions, tend to secure funding and resources more effectively for water infrastructure projects. Specifically, factors like transparent performance metrics, channels for customer feedback, and sustainable funding approaches played crucial roles in the achievement of the availability of water services in urban centres. Additionally, achieving inclusive water services often hinged on fostering community engagement in decision-making processes. Likewise, this study's main focus was on decision-making excluding financial control impact on water availability.

Furthermore, findings from the study conducted by Tuli and Makarius S.C. L (2018) on Institutional challenges for water management in the Pangani River Basin of Tanzania, revealed that poor decision-making, characterized by inadequate coordination, diverging stakeholder interests, and institutional incompatibility, significantly constrained watershed management integration and predisposed watersheds to unsustainable management practices. These challenges highlight the critical role of good decision-making in advancing integrated water resources management and ensuring the availability of clean water for community members. Thus, this study underscored

challenges that the PBWI faces in water management, yet, excluding crucial aspects of financial planning in enhancing water management for domestic use.

Generally, the empirical literature reviewed reveals a noticeable gap that persists in the specific investigation of the interrelationships between financial control, decision-making, and water availability within the Pangani River Basin. While existing research focuses on the individual components of financial planning, such as budgetary processes, community participation, decision-making for financial matters, and institutional challenges, rarely studies comprehensively analyse how the financial control and decision-making components of financial planning collectively influence water availability for domestic use. Thus, a research gap exists in understanding the influence of financial planning based on financial control and decision-making practices on water availability within the study area, justifying further the need for investigation to address this gap and inform evidence-based policy interventions.

The Conceptual Framework

The following conceptual framework in figure 1. reflects the researcher's understanding of the theoretical and empirical literature review;

Fig. 1: The Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework illustrates the interrelationships between key variables derived from both theoretical understandings and empirical evidence. Grounded in the theoretical literature review, the framework explains how financial control, financial decision-making, and water availability are interconnected within the context of the Pangani River Basin in Tanzania. Financial planning emphasises the importance of proper financial control and decision-making for domestic water availability. Financial control

is important in ensuring efficiency in financial resource management mechanisms, including budgetary controls and monitoring its direct use. Financial decision-making, emphasises stakeholder participation and proper decision processes as a critical determinant of water availability.

Materials and Methods

The Study Area

The Pangani River Basin in the Korogwe District, Tanga Region, Tanzania, is chosen as the study area due to its critical role as a primary water source for the domestic and agricultural needs of the community along the Pangani River. This selection was underpinned by its importance to local livelihoods and economic activities, making it an appropriate context for investigating the impact of financial planning on water availability. Furthermore, the Pangani Basin Water Institute enabled the researcher to access relevant data on water resource management, given its central role in overseeing water allocation and policy implementation.

Moreover, the Pangani River Basin presents a distinct set of challenges in water resource management, including issues such as water scarcity and competing demands for allocation. Focusing on this specific geographical area allows for an important exploration of factors influencing water availability, offering contextually relevant findings that can inform targeted interventions and policy measures. Ultimately, by conducting the study in the Pangani Basin, the research aims to address the region's water management challenges, facilitating evidence-based decision-making and fostering sustainable access to water resources for communities within and beyond the basin.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

The research surveyed 1,160 households across four villages in the Korogwe district, Tanga Region. The visited villages are Hale, Kwasunga, Kilole and Jitengeni along the Pangani river basin and engaged 17 Pangani Water Institution workers. The study applied the Slovin (1967) formula to determine the sample, and a stratified random sampling technique with a 10% intensity resulting in the selection of 116 respondents from the 1,160 households, ensuring representation and balance. The population was stratified into four distinct strata to accommodate variations in water dependency and usage patterns. The survey targeted household heads for participation, with any 18-year-old household member randomly chosen if the head was unavailable or unwilling to participate.

The sampling strategy ensured a collection of diverse perspectives and experiences from participants related to water availability and usage within the Pangani River Basin. For key informants, a purposive sampling method was employed to select 17 Pangani Water Institution workers as key informants. The selection was based on participants' roles, managerial positions and expertise in water management within the Pangani River Basin. The selection aimed to gather insights from key stakeholders directly involved in financial planning and decision-making processes, providing a helpful perspective on the institutional aspects influencing water availability for domestic use.

Data Collection Techniques

The study utilised a mixed-method approach, incorporating quantitative and qualitative methods to gather comprehensive data. The primary methods included structured surveys and semi-structured interviews, facilitated by specific tools designed for these purposes. The dual-method approach ensured a comprehensive understanding of the study's objectives, allowing for triangulation and validation of findings to enhance the overall reliability and validity of the research outcomes.

Data Collection Methods and Tools

Structured surveys were employed to collect quantitative data from 1,160 households in the Pangani River Basin. This method was chosen for its efficiency in gathering standardised information from many respondents. A detailed questionnaire was developed for the household surveys. This tool included a series of closed-ended questions to capture data on financial planning, water availability, and usage patterns. The questionnaire was pre-tested in a pilot study to ensure clarity and reliability. Field researchers administered the surveys face-to-face with household heads during data collection, providing necessary clarifications to ensure accurate and comprehensive data collection. In cases where the head of the household was unavailable, any adult member (aged 18 or above) was selected to participate.

Semi-structured interviews were conducted with 17 key informants from the Pangani Basin Water Institute. This qualitative method allowed for in-depth exploration of institutional dynamics and provided rich contextual data to complement the survey findings. An interview guide was used to collect data for the semi-structured interviews. This tool comprised open-ended questions that facilitated detailed discussions on financial planning practices, decision-making processes, and challenges in water resource management. Interviews were conducted in person, recorded (with permission), and transcribed for detailed analysis. The flexible nature of semi-structured interviews allowed the researchers to probe deeper into specific issues as they arose during the conversation.

Data Analysis Technique

The study analysed data using arithmetic, correlation analysis, and multiple linear regressions to understand the impact of financial controlling, and decision-making on water availability. Inferential statistics were used for conclusions, and tests were conducted to ensure data reliability. The multiple linear regression equation which was used to determine the relationship between independent variables and dependent variables is presented in the following equation:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e$$

Where:

- Y= Dependent Variable (Availability of clean water)

- α = Constant;
- β =Beta Coefficients
- X1= Financial Controlling
- X2= Financial decision-making
- e= Error Term at 95% confidence level.

Thematic analysis was utilised to analyse qualitative data from in-depth interviews. Thematic analysis involves systematically identifying, analysing, and interpreting patterns or themes within the qualitative data. This approach allowed the exploration of the underlying meanings, experiences, and perspectives shared by participants regarding water management and financial planning. The themes emerging from the qualitative data were coded and organised into meaningful categories, providing a deeper understanding of the themes generated related to water availability in the study area.

Results

Reliability and Validity Testing

Reliability Testing

The reliability of the research instruments was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient Test for each latent variable. The results as presented in Table 1 indicated a good level of reliability for all constructs, with Cronbach's Alpha coefficients exceeding the standard threshold of 0.7, suggesting a high level of internal consistency among the items used in the study.

Table 1. Reliability Statistics Results

Construct	Cronbach's Alpha	No. of Items
Financial Control	0.812	4
Financial Decision-making	0.834	4
Water Availability	0.798	4

The findings in Table 1 present the reliability scores for each construct, confirming that the items used to measure each latent variable are consistent and reliable.

Multicollinearity Testing

Multicollinearity tests were conducted to ensure the independence of the variables. As illustrated in Table 2, the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) and tolerance statistics revealed no significant multicollinearity issues. The VIF values for financial control and decision-making are below 10, indicating low multicollinearity, while the tolerance statistics were above 0.2, further confirming the independence of the variables.

Table 2. Multicollinearity Test Results

	Tolerance	VIF
Financial Control	0.343	2.918
Financial Decision	0.351	2.852

The results from the multicollinearity tests in Table 2 ensure that the variables used in the regression analysis are independent and not highly correlated with each other, thus validating the use of these variables in the subsequent analysis.

Regression Analysis

Multiple regression analysis was conducted to assess the impact of financial control and financial decision-making on the availability of clean water for domestic use in the Pangani River Basin. The model for the relationship is represented by the following linear equation:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e$$

Where:

Y represents the availability of clean water for domestic use (dependent variable)

α denotes the constant term

β_1 and β_2 represent the beta coefficients for financial control and financial decision-making, respectively

X1 and X2 represent financial control and financial decision-making as independent variables

e represents the error term

Evaluating the Model

The model exhibits good predictive capabilities as indicated in Table 3, with financial control, and decision-making identified as the best predictors of domestic water availability. The R-square value (0.692) indicates that 69.2% water availability variance can be explained by the independent variable. Additionally, the Durbin-Watson statistic of 2.098 suggests no autocorrelation within the data.

Table 3. Model Summary

Model	R	R. Squire	Adj R Squire	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change R Squire	F. Change	Df1	Df2	Sig	Dublin Watson
1	.832	.692	.685	.30077	.692	96.713	3	129	.000	2.098

Statistical Significance of Results

The ANOVA test in Table 4 revealed a significant regression model, as evidenced by the p-value of less than 0.05, indicating that the relationship between the independent variables of financial planning (financial control, and financial decision-making) and the dependent variable (availability of clean water for domestic use) was statistically significant.

Table 4. ANOVA Table

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	26.247	3	8.749	96.713	.000
Residual	11.670	129	.090		
Total	37.916	132			

Results of Multiple Regressions

Table 5 presents the results of the multiple regression analysis, indicating the unstandardised and standardised coefficients, and their respective significance levels. Both financial control and decision-making were found to have a significant positive impact on the availability of clean water for domestic use.

Table 5. Multiple Regression Results

	Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	1.355	.195		6.948	.000
Financial control	.377	.059	.535	6.412	.000
Financial decision	.326	.070	.383	4.645	.000

Discussion of the Findings

This section presents a comprehensive analysis of the study's findings. The aim is to uncover the complexities of the influence of financial planning on water availability for domestic use in the Pangani Basin, Tanzania. The discussion explores the statistical results obtained from various analytical techniques, supplemented by qualitative findings from key informants. The findings aimed to generate an understanding of the relationship between financial planning and water resource availability.

The Influence of financial control on the availability of water for domestic use in the Pangani Water Basin

Accessibility of clean water for domestic use is highly associated with the respective water management institutions' ability to control finances to ensure communities near water sources benefit from the surrounding water resources (Gbedemah, Eshun,

Frimpong, & Okine, 2022). In connection with that, this study explored the impact of financial control on domestic water availability in the Pangani Water Basin, Tanzania.

The study findings revealed a significant positive impact of financial control on water availability for domestic use ($\beta = 0.377$, $p < 0.001$). This implies a corresponding increase in domestic water availability for every unit increase in financial planning. These statistical results align strongly with the Resource Dependence Theory explained by Pfeffer and Salancik (1978), emphasising the multifaceted nature of water supply projects and the critical role of effective financial management.

In-depth interviews with officials from the Pangani Basin Water revealed the essential role of financial control practices in ensuring the sustainability and equitable distribution of water resources within the Pangani Water Basin. One participant stated, "*Effective financial control which includes proper budgeting and utilisation of the funds is essential for ensuring that we secure the right amount of funds from Banks and user service charges, and utilise them efficiently and equitably across water projects within the basin. We are careful in making budgets for maintaining water infrastructure, and use the budget according to the plan.*" This sentiment highlights the critical role of financial control in enhancing resource allocation and utilisation for sustainable water management.

The findings from indepth interviews further revealed that through financial control, the Pangani Water Basin Institute have managed to improve infrastructure such as water distribution networks and water treatment plants. The other participant said "*each month we try to make good use of the funds we budgeted for to repair pipelines, storage tanks, and purify water to remove contamination*". These findings shows that the PBWI control finances for ensuring that infrastructure are well maintained for sustainable water supply to the community living nearby.

These findings are in line with the findings of Liu, Chen, Wang, Wang, and Zhang (2023) who observed that financial control is vital for ensuring access to clean water in the management of water basins due to the prevalent of challenges such as funding shortages, high repairing and material purchasing costs, and balancing business strategies with social equity in Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM). Likewise, Gorelick, Gold and Asefa (2023) emphasised the importance of using correct financial models for water projects before making financial decisions, thus, enhancing supply reliability and stability in water services provision.

Emphasising the importance of transparent financial control mechanisms and stakeholder engagement, a participant from the Pangani Basin Water highlighted the role of capacity building in enhancing financial management practices. One participant stated, "*Investing in training and capacity-building programs for staff members is crucial for strengthening financial control measures particularly budgeting processes and ensuring compliance with regulatory requirements. In each quarter of the financial year, we take a few staff from the accounts department for training.*" This acknowledgement highlights the institution's commitment to continuous improvement and professional development, recognising that well-trained personnel are essential for effective financial management.

The emphasis on capacity building underscores the importance of human resources in implementing and maintaining financial control measures. Likewise, research by Oyelakin and Abdullahi (2022) emphasises the importance of training staff on financial matters so that well-trained employees contribute to enhanced financial accountability and the successful implementation of financial control measures in various organisational settings. This suggests that investing in human capital through training and skill development programs can enhance organisational capacity to manage financial resources efficiently.

The Effect of Financial Decision-Making on Domestic Water Availability

Decision-making is an essential tool in facilitating the availability of social services to the community (Mahbub Hasan, 2022). Accordingly, the study examined the influence of financial decision-making on domestic water availability within the Pangani Water Basin. Quantitative analysis revealed a significant positive correlation between financial decision-making and water availability ($\beta = 0.326$, $p < 0.05$) meaning a unit increase in proper financial decision-making results in a 0.326 increase in water accessibility. These statistical findings indicate that effective financial decision-making processes contribute to improved domestic water availability in the region.

This finding suggests that decisions related to financial resource allocation and investment in water infrastructure are important in ensuring adequate water supply for domestic use. In the Pangani Water Basin, this finding implies that effective financial decision-making enhances the organisation's ability to meet the water needs of local communities. During an in-depth interview, the key informant from the Pangani Water Basin stated, "*We prioritise investments in water infrastructure based on thorough cost-benefit analyses and community needs assessments.*" This highlights the institution's commitment to evidence-based decision-making and resource allocation strategies, contributing to improved water availability for domestic use. This finding corresponds with Muzayanah's (2022) observation that in Curug, Karawang, community-driven fiscal control of water projects, plays important role in ensuring transparency and accountability in financial management practices.

Another participant underscored the importance of stakeholder engagement in financial decision-making "*We involve local communities in water project planning through village meetings to ensure that their needs and priorities are adequately addressed.*" This participatory approach to decision-making aligns with principles of inclusive governance and community empowerment, ultimately enhancing the effectiveness of financial investments in water projects. This finding aligns with the research findings by Dral, Witte and Hartmann (2023) who found that municipalities with participatory decision-making processes were more likely to prioritise investments in water infrastructure and maintenance. Similarly, Trimmer, Qureshi, Otoo and Delaire (2023) revealed that communities with inclusive decision-making processes tend to secure funding and resources more effectively for water infrastructure projects, thus enabling them to secure sufficient water for their needs.

These findings underscore the critical role of financial decision-making in shaping water availability outcomes within the Pangani Water Basin. By emphasising making

relevant decisions and promoting stakeholder engagement, water management institutions can enhance their capacity to address water challenges and ensure sustainable access to clean water for local communities.

The Conceptual Mode of the Financial Planning Impact on Water Availability

Fig 2. Financial Planning Impact on Water Availability

The conceptual mode presented in Fig 2 visually represents the positive impacts of financial control and financial decision-making on the availability of clean water for domestic use in the Pangani Water Basin. The Financial Control and Financial Decision-Making are the independent variables, and the Availability of Clean Water is the dependent variable. The arrows indicate the direction of influence from the independent variables to the dependent variable, in which the financial control enhances the improved infrastructure for water provision and the financial decision-making facilitates the allocation of more water for domestic use demonstrating the significant positive impact each has on water availability.

Conclusion

This study highlights the impact of financial planning, particularly focusing on financial controlling and decision-making, on water accessibility for domestic use in the Pangani Water Basin, Tanzania. Combining quantitative analysis with qualitative insights from key informants, the research highlights the key role of effective financial management practices in ensuring continuing access to clean water for local communities. It stresses the importance of relevant financial planning while emphasising the significance of adhering to financial control mechanisms, such as budget focus on community needs and proper fund utilisation. Furthermore, the study underscores the value of a community participatory decision-making process as it provides bases for relevant institutional financial decisions towards sustainable water availability for domestic use.

Recommendations

Based on the study findings, the following recommendations are proposed: The management in Pangani Water Basin should emphasise financial control particularly proper budgeting and effective use of the allocated budgets for ensuring water availability. For sustainable results, continuous emphasis should be on stakeholders' engagement in decision-making processes such as the local communities and government agencies to enable the institution ensure water management initiatives are aligned with community needs and priorities. Moreover, there should also be a continued investment in capacity-building programs for water management professionals and staff members. This can improve human capacity to implement transparent financial control mechanisms and make evidence-based decisions regarding water infrastructure investments.

Areas for Further Studies

Since water availability for domestic use can be affected by other factors such as climatic change, future studies could explore the impact of climate change on water availability and the effectiveness of adaptation strategies in mitigating water scarcity in the Pangani region. Other studies could focus on understanding community perceptions, attitudes, and behaviours related to water management. This is essential for designing effective interventions and policies.

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